

NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER

YEAR 3 ANNUAL REPORT

OCTOBER, 2007

NESCENT ANNUAL REPORT YEAR 3

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I YEAR 3 ANNUAL REPORT SUMMARY

During year 3 NESCent continued its maturation as a Center for the promotion of activities leading to a “grand synthesis” in evolutionary biology. The achievements of the Center are detailed in the subsequent sections of this report. Briefly, they include:

- In year 3 the Center functioned with a full complement of postdoctoral fellows and sabbatical scholars. This group contributes to a vital intellectual atmosphere at the Center, and has numerous interactions with visiting working and catalysis groups and the surrounding University communities. They have generated a wide variety of products, including publications, grants, new databases, and analytical tools and software.
- We have hosted a variety of meetings over the past 12 months including over 30 meetings of NESCent funded working, catalysis, informatics and education groups. We have also hosted several additional groups, bringing a total of over 800 scientists to the Center over the past 12 months. NESCent sponsored activities have already contributed to significant advances in evolutionary biology.
- We have an outstanding Informatics program, with excellent staff and the full range of infrastructural services to support our scientific programs.
- The Informatics staff has supported in-house and visiting scientists in a variety of ways, and has partnered with external groups to obtain three external awards (NIH and NSF), with two additional proposals pending.
- The Center, in partnership with the Metadata Research Center at UNC Chapel Hill, has made significant strides towards the development of a data repository for evolutionary biology, DRYAD. A major grant to support his effort has been submitted.
- Our Education and Outreach group has developed new focus for its activities. Efforts are centered on the communication of NESCent science, developing partnerships to improve and support evolutionary biology teaching and research at historically minority serving institutions, and to improve the teaching of evolutionary biology. One major NSF grant to develop innovative curricular materials for evolutionary biology is pending.
- The EOG group has completed a number of highly successful outreach activities, including co-sponsoring a symposium on modern evolutionary biology at the National Association of Biology Teachers annual conference and a program at the Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science meeting.
- We have offered a variety of training opportunities and courses, ranging from advanced computational techniques, to a postdoctoral fellow professional development series to a workshop in teaching evolutionary biology to elementary school students.
- We have a broad range of activities directed towards the recruitment of underrepresented groups into evolutionary biology. These activities span all branches of the Center.
- The administrative infrastructure of the Center has made enormous progress, with a new administrative database and redesigned website, and a whole range of procedures, policies and activities developed that allow the Center administration to efficiently and effectively support NESCent sponsored science.

II NESCENT OVERARCHING GOALS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

NESCent's overarching goals include

- To facilitate and support high quality science, in particular synthetic and interdisciplinary activities in evolutionary biology.
- To position ourselves to play a leading role in development and dissemination of informatics tools for evolutionary biology
- To provide information, outreach and educational resources to the scientific community
- To reach out to the broader community, including educators and members of groups underrepresented in evolutionary biology to increase understanding of and participation in evolutionary biology

Although since its inception, NESCent has been organized into three distinct branches, Science and Synthesis, Informatics, and Education and Outreach, these branches and activities are increasingly integrated. For example, Informatics programs are essential to most scientific activities of the Center. Commitment towards the recruitment of underrepresented groups is integral to Center function and spans all our programs. Several of our important informatics initiatives are in fact educational, and our EOG group interacts extensively with our science programs, providing general support and dissemination of results. Therefore although the organization of this document to some degree reflects these historic divisions, the separation into independent branches is increasingly artificial. NESCent Directors and staff members work as a team, with each contributing to the development of all aspects of NESCent activities.

In this report the activities of each branch are outlined; however, we also focus on several Center-wide activities such as education, outreach to underrepresented groups, products from NESCent funded activities, partnerships and external funding.

III SCIENCE AND SYNTHESIS: ACTIVITIES, FINDINGS AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS

Synthetic research in evolutionary biology occurs along a continuum in terms of the scope of the scientific questions, tools and disciplines that may be involved. At one end of the continuum, synthesis involves integrating available data and models to address important problems within a discipline. Such research is essential for quantitatively evaluating the current state of a field, revealing important general patterns and results, and identifying critical gaps and promising directions for future research. At the other end, methods and perspectives from multiple disciplines are combined to develop new tools for answering, and creating new, fundamental scientific questions. NESCent's strategy for Science and Synthesis is to develop and support a portfolio of scientific activities that spans this spectrum of synthetic research in evolutionary biology and related fields.

Towards achieving this scientific portfolio, Science and Synthesis at NESCent has focused on five major goals during the past year: a) to maintain effective and open application and review processes, b) to attract and support a diverse and high-quality portfolio of research projects, c) to establish a vibrant and collegial in-house research community, d) to develop new scientific initiatives that broaden NESCent's reach and scope, and e) to assess and ensure the productivity and impact of NESCent scientific activities. As summarized below, we have achieved or made significant progress on each of these goals during the past year.

Application and review processes

Our on-line application, review and Board evaluation systems are now established and fully operational. We have established a regular schedule for applications, with deadlines of 15 June and 1 December each year. To expand our sabbatical application we now consider sabbatical applications twice a year. We have established the guidelines for proposals, criteria for evaluation, and conflict of interest policies, all of which are available on our web site.

We expanded the Science Review Board to 23 members, to increase our expertise in bioinformatics and computational biology, and maintained the excellence and diversity of the Board in terms of field, rank, gender and background (see current membership at http://www.nescent.org/dir/science_board.php). We will be adding several new board members this fall to maintain continuity as founding board members begin to rotate off at the end of their 3-year terms starting in winter 2008.

We have established application, evaluation and support processes for NESCent and NCEAS (National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis) to jointly sponsor working group projects that integrate evolutionary and ecological synthesis. We have, as of October, 2007, awarded three joint projects to date, one of which has met thus far.

To expand faculty participation at NESCent, we recently established a Short-term Visitors program. This supports short visits at NESCent by faculty and other scientists for 2 weeks to 3 months. Applications are short, with deadlines 4 times a year; the applications are reviewed by several Science Board members and the Directors, allowing a rapid turn around time. We particularly emphasize collaborative and multi-investigator proposals, and see this as a way to bring many new scientists to the Center. We received 4 proposals for our September 1 deadline that we are now evaluating.

Scientific Activities and New Initiatives

We had two application deadlines in year 3 (Dec 06 and June 07) that attracted 60 proposals, and resulted in 12 awards including 2 postdoctoral fellows, 2 sabbatical scholars, 7 working groups and 1 catalysis meetings (see Table 1 for summary and appendix III.1 for complete listing of activities funded in year 3).

Table 1: summary of year 3 proposals received, ranking (Hi Priority, Fund if Funds Available, or Do Not Fund) offers, and awards.

Type	Proposals	Hi Priority	FIFA	Do Not Fund	Offer	Accept
Postdoc	33	5	21	7	4	2
Sabbatical	5	1	3	1	3	2
Working Group	16	6	8	2	7	7
Catalysis Meeting	6	1	2	3	1	1
Total	60	13	34	13	15	12

The complete listing of NESCent scientific projects funded through year 3 is provided on our webpage (see <http://www.nescent.org/science/awards.php>). In response to questions on the breadth of science funded by NESCent raised by the year 2 site visit team, we examined the areas covered by NESCent funded science. We found that collectively, our funded activities address a diversity of fundamental evolutionary questions in evolution, systematics and comparative biology and cover most, if not all, important areas of evolutionary biology. Our interpretation was endorsed by our Senior Advisory Board at their August meeting.

Table 2: summary of NESCent awards to date (September 07) in terms of subject areas (each proposal is classified in terms of two areas of focus).

<u>Subject area:</u>	<u>Area 1</u>	<u>Area 2</u>
Genomics/Proteomics	7	6
Molecular evolution	2	8
Development	0	2
Physiology/Functional Morphology	4	4
Behavior/Neurobiology	3	2
Medicine	0	2
Evol. Ecology/Popn Biology	8	7
Evolutionary Genetics	7	6
Phylogeography/Speciation	3	4
Comparative Biology	7	6
Systematics/Phylogenetics	9	7
Paleontology	6	2
Education	3	3

This summary demonstrates that our scientific research portfolio includes a wide range of approaches and biological levels of organization within evolutionary biology and associated fields.

Based on recommendations from our advisory boards, we have initiated an optional third year of funding for postdoctoral fellows. Fellows may apply for a third year funding; these proposals are evaluated by the Science Review Board and the Operations Committee. Proposals are evaluated based on the accomplishments of the applicants during their first two years, and the potential that additional funding will enable fellows to expand their projects in exciting new directions. Three postdoctoral fellows were awarded 3rd-year funding this year.

We have established a vibrant and collegial community of in-house scientists. This currently includes 12 postdoctoral fellows (1 more to arrive by Jan 2008), 2 sabbatical scholars, 2 Triangle research fellows, and several visiting scientists. This community has a regular seminar series, at least one new in house working group, a professional development series for postdocs, a journal club, active intranet communications, a Darwin Day scientific symposium, and a host of new social traditions. (Appendices III.2 & III.3)

We have seen our first cohort of postdoctoral fellows leave NESCent. Two have moved onto further postdoctoral positions (including a NSF Minority Research Fellowship) and three have accepted tenure track faculty positions (Appendix III.4).

We have supported and hosted 19 meetings by catalysis and working groups during the past year, including meetings by all of the groups funded in the first round (Appendix III.5). In addition we have supported an addition 20 meeting from Center funds (including education, and informatics activities, and other programs funded from sources other than then core grant, and hosted 8 meetings by a variety of groups involved in evolutionary synthesis, but not supported by NESCent funds. Detailed participant lists can be found in Appendices III.6 - III.8; demographics and other characteristics of NESCent funded scientists are in Appendices III.9 & III.10.

Products

The first scientific activities funded by NESCent began in the summer and fall of 2005, just over 2 years ago. As a result most of the outcomes and products of these activities are ongoing. Nevertheless, based on the reports by NESCent participants through mid-September 2007 we can clearly document the success of synthetic research supported by NESCent. These products are listed in Section IX of this report. Thus far, NESCent funded research activities have resulted in 65 articles published or in press, with an additional 26 publications in review or in preparation. Sabbatical fellows and working groups have contributed the most to these totals thus far. There have been 12 successful grant proposals, with 11 additional proposals submitted or in preparation as a result of activities funded by NESCent. We are encouraged that catalysis meetings have been notably successful in generating grants and proposals as well as new collaborations: these meetings have been important in generating new research and new research directions at NESCent. Hosted meetings and other activities (Other) have also contributed importantly to productivity at NESCent in a variety of ways.

Table 3: Summary of NESCent products (through mid-September 2007). See section IX of this report for a full listing. (Numbers in parentheses indicate publications or grants in preparation.)

<u>Products:</u>	Postdoc	Sabbatical	Work Group	Catalysis Meetings	Other	Totals
Publications	8 (6)	33 (4)	18 (9)	2 (2)	4 (5)	65 (26)
Grants/Proposals	2 (0)	3 (0)	3 (1)	2 (6)	2 (4)	12 (11)
Software	5	1	3	0	7	16
Collaborations	8	5	4	6	9	32

Priorities for year 4

The goals for science and synthesis for the coming year are to maintain and extend the strength and diversity of our portfolio of scientific activities at NESCent, and to ensure their productivity and impact. Many of our groups have already scheduled meetings for year 4 (Appendix III.11), and we expect to host approximately the same number of visitors to the Center in year 4. Plans for new awards in years 4-5 are summarized in Table 3. Because postdoctoral fellows and working groups are multi-year awards, we expect to continue to have a vibrant program in year 5.

Table 4: planned awards in years 4 & 5

Type	2008	2009
Postdoc	5	0
Sabbatical scholars	4	3
Working groups & Catalysis meetings	8	0

There are several priorities for developing scientific activities in the coming year.

- The number of strong proposals we are receiving for sabbaticals at NESCent is more limited than for the other activity types (see Tables 1-2). We have made the sabbatical program more flexible in terms of deadlines, duration and timing, and started a new Short-term Visitors program (see above). We are focusing our scientific outreach efforts on promoting and attracting more applications for faculty for these programs.
- We have worked hard to ensure that we reach all potential audiences with our calls for proposals. NESCent was represented at a wide variety of scientific meetings, and

advertised our call for proposals broadly (Appendices III.12 & III.13). However we must continue to ensure we reach all appropriate audiences within and beyond evolutionary biology. In particular we must ensure that groups under-represented in evolutionary biology are recruited to participate in Center activities.

- A fundamental issue is to understand the dynamics of scientific collaborations in promoting productive and innovative synthetic research in evolution: how do group size, disciplinary and other components of diversity and other factors impact productivity of NESCent activities? We have begun collaboration with social and information scientists from UNC and elsewhere to apply social network analysis and related approaches to explore these issues, and to ensure that we are collecting all the relevant data we will need to develop the appropriate assessment tools as we go forward.
- New initiatives: During the past year we have developed ideas for several major initiatives in promoting broad synthesis in evolutionary biology. Feedback from the Senior Advisory Board at our August 2007 meeting helped us to focus our efforts on two major priorities in the next 2 years:

Evolution 2020. We will commission a series of short synthetic essays (~1500 words) on where the field of evolution should be in another decade. These essays will be produced in a variety of ways; some may be commissioned papers, some will grow out of our sponsored science, while others will be the result of specially convened workshops, seminars and small meetings.

Evolutionary genomics and the Tree of Life. We will begin a series of collaborations in order to facilitate the integration of organismal phylogenies (e.g. AToL projects) into genomics tools and databases (e.g. NCBI taxonomies).

- We will continue to seek and encourage proposals for activities that expand evolutionary biology into areas not central to the enterprise, such as medicine and cell and molecular biology.

IV INFORMATICS: INITIATIVES, ACTIVITIES AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS

NESCent provides hardware and software, network infrastructure, electronic collaboration resources, scientific computing support, and high-performance computing resources for working groups, catalysis meetings, postdoctoral and sabbatical fellows, and Center administration. NESCent is also an active partner in a variety of community cyberinfrastructure initiatives that promote synthetic evolutionary biology through software interoperability and usability, data sharing and informatics training. There are currently 9 full-time Informatics staff positions supported by both core and external funds, five of which are new this year. Eight are currently filled. (See Appendix IV.1)

Major Initiatives

Open development of open-source, evolutionary bioinformatics software

The 2006 Phyloinformatics Hackathon, an event designed to build community and capacity for the open development of open-source evolutionary bioinformatics software, was described in the previous annual report. This unique meeting is more fully described in an upcoming paper in *Evolutionary Bioinformatics* (Lapp et al. in press; Appendix IV.2). The next hackathon, on Comparative Phylogenetic Methods in R is currently being planned for December 2007. It is being co-organized with NESCent postdocs Brian O'Meara, Samantha Price and Amy Zanne, as well as Steve Kembel from the University of California at Berkeley, and grew out of a whitepaper submitted by Price and Zanne. For more information on plans as they progress, see http://hackathon.nescent.org/R_Hackathon_1.

Digital data sharing

Work continues in collaboration with Jane Greenberg of the UNC School of Information and Library Sciences Metadata Research Center (MRC) on design of a digital data repository for preservation and sharing of published datasets in evolutionary biology. A system architect, Dr. Ryan Scherle, was hired in August 2007 and is working full time on the Phase I repository, named Dryad, which is based largely on the open-source repository software DSpace. A major workshop to guide the development of Phase II was held in May, and attended by both experts from information science and stakeholders from the evolutionary biology community (Appendix IV.3). In collaboration with MRC, the North Carolina State University Digital Library Program, TreeBASE, and the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) Network, a proposal was submitted to the NSF DBI program in July to fund this work (Appendix IV.4). The proposal includes letters of support from a variety of evolutionary biology societies and journals (including the *American Naturalist*, *Evolution*, *Integrative and Comparative Biology*, *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*, *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, *Molecular Ecology*, and *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*). The relevant societies and journals expressed support for the broad principles of a Data Archiving Policy drafted by NESCent sabbatical scholar Michael Whitlock (see Appendix IV.3).

We have also participated in an INTEROP proposal led by William Michener of the LTER Network (Appendix IV.5). The proposal grew out of an NSF-sponsored series of workshops on Data Sharing organized by the Ecological Society of America. The last workshop in this series, focusing on Obstacles to Data Sharing was hosted at NESCent in May. The proposal is intended to lay the groundwork for community capacity and new technologies to support the design, implementation, and deployment of a Virtual Data Center (VDC) for biodiversity, ecological and

environmental data. The VDC is envisioned to be founded on open standards and protocols for interoperability among existing and new data centers.

Management of genome data from evolutionary model organisms

Funding has been obtained to provide greater user support for the Generic Model Organism Database project through an NIH grant with Ian Holmes and Lincoln Stein (see Summary in Appendix IV.6). User support specialist David Clements has been hired to fill this position. Through this project, NESCent will be able to provide badly needed support to the variety of small research communities developing genomic resources for evolutionary organisms. In the past year, NESCent contract staff Brian Osborne already substantially revamped the online documentation for the project (www.gmod.org). Clements is continuing to centralize documentation for the distributed project, contributing to new documentation for heavily used GMOD components, developing training workshops to be held at NESCent, developing tutorials to be disseminated online and at multiple scientific meeting each year, and is responding to user queries on the GMOD mailing lists.

Management of evolutionary phenotype data using ontologies

Funding was obtained for a major collaboration with Paula Mabee and Monte Westerfield, pioneering the application of phenotype ontologies to comparative morphological data (Appendix IV.7). This grew out of a NESCent working group led by Mabee and Westerfield titled "Towards an Integrated Database for Fish Evolution." Two programmer FTEs at NESCent are responsible for developing data curation software, a knowledge-base and web interface. One of these positions was been filled by Dr. James Balhoff, who has since made substantial contributions to the open source software package Phenote (www.phenote.org). Phenote is being used by project staff to curate phenotype data in the teleosts using anatomical and trait quality ontologies. A needs analysis workshop was held at NESCent in September 2007 that brought together nine distinguished researchers in evolution, development and genetics to provide guidance for the design of a Knowledge Base that integrates evolutionary phenotypes with model organism genetic data. NESCent is also in the process of co-organizing community engagement workshops on phenotype ontologies together with the National Center for Biomedical Ontologies, the first of which will be at the 2008 Evolution meetings

Training Activities

Training in the tools and techniques of evolutionary informatics is a major focus of the Informatics program. To this end our Informatics team initiated several activities, discussed further in Section IV, Center Courses, Workshops and Educational Programs.

Support for Sponsored Science

A variety of small programming projects in support of individual scientists and workings groups have been undertaken in the past year. Those projects that involved greater programming effort, and resulted in generally useful products, deserve special mention:

GeoPhyloBuilder

The beta version of GeoPhyloBuilder, software for manipulation and visualization of phylogeographic data within a GIS framework, developed by NESCent postdoc David Kidd and NESCent informatics staff Xinhua Liu, was released in January 2007 (Kidd and Liu 2007,

<http://www.nescent.org/informatics/software.php>). The latest version can export data to Google Earth, and a web application is currently under development that would allow even researchers unfamiliar with GIS tools to visualize a 3D phylogeny projected onto a map.

Chado diversity module for Butterflybase

In a project that was initiated by sabbatical scholar Owen McMillan, NESCent informatics staff Hilmar Lapp and Xianhua Liu, together with contract staff Nassib Nassar and Brian Osborne, developed a data model for phenotype and genotype variation that is interoperable with other data model components of the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) schema, known as Chado. McMillan's close collaborator, Chris Jiggins of Cambridge University, has sought UK funding to build upon the prototype database and web application developed by NESCent for this project and to incorporate it into a future version of ButterflyBase (www.butterflybase.org). The diversity module is currently being reviewed for possible inclusion into the standard Chado distribution.

Plant Mixed Mating Evolution Database

NESCent informatics staff Hilmar Lapp, Xianhua Liu and Surya Dhullipalla released a beta version of a database and web-based user interface for the "Paradox of Mixed Mating in Plants" working group. The database is designed to manage information from a large number of studies of plant mating systems in support of the meta-analysis goals of the working group. The database will be made public and become an extendible community resource once the meta-analysis results of the group have been published.

Additional activities in support of sponsored science

Additional major database projects have been initiated with the Phanerozoic Body Size Trends and the Primate Life Histories working groups, and postdocs Brian Sidlauskas, Amy Zanne and Samantha Price. All of these are intended to result in community resources upon completion.

Information Technology Support

NESCent Website

A redesigned NESCent website was launched in January 2007, with rich and dynamic content. Community use has increased significantly (Appendix IV.8). In March of year 3 we added an electronic news feed, which can be used by other organizations to syndicate news about NESCent's on-going activities. In addition, we maintain a well-used wiki that serves as an intranet to which NESCent's staff and long-term scientific visitors can post and from which they can retrieve information about Center operations, projects, events, etc.

Support for Basic Center Operations

The first phase of a comprehensive administrative database and web interface has been developed in-house. The NESCent Administrative Database (NEAD) manages the submission and review of proposals, information on people, projects, and activities at the Center, and collects and manages reports of accomplishments from sponsored scientists. The database also assists in preparing Center-wide reports.

Improvements to IT Infrastructure

We have continued to add to our capacity for high-performance computing on the Duke Shared Cluster Resource. We have purchased new equipment which allows us to provide regularly backed-up fileserver space to Center staff and long-term scientists, and to reconfigure our network and hardware system to provide more optimal database, web, and other services. Shared equipment is now kept in a climate-controlled server room equipped with UPS and high-capacity network connections. Together with the EOG we have increased our capacity for multi-media products, video streaming and so forth, which aids greatly in Center outreach.

Informatics Advisory Group

When the Informatics group was reorganized in early 2006 an Informatics Advisory group was constituted. This group is currently chaired by Michael Sanderson and also includes John Alroy, Matt Jones, Sudhir Kumar, Joseph Neigel, Kimmen Sjolander and Jason Stajich. In early August, the IAG was given a written brief on NESCent's Informatics activities, met via teleconference, and provided a written report to the Center. This report was shared with members of Senior Advisory Board in August. The SAB recommended that this group need no longer serve as a formal advisory and review group but instead be used as a group of experts to provide informal advice as necessary. We will move forward with this recommendation.

Informatics Priorities for Year 4

The most important priorities for the Informatics program in year 4 include the following:

- Development of the first phase of the Dryad digital data repository.
- Continuing to improve support, training and dissemination for GMOD in the evolutionary genomics community, including a summer workshop for emerging model organisms.
- Continuing to develop informatics tools for management and analysis of evolutionary phenotype data, in collaboration with ZFIN, CToL, the NCBO, and other partners, including a summer workshop to be held at the 2008 Evolution Meetings (ASN/SSB/SSE).
- Developing partnerships with emerging informatics initiatives including the Plant Science Cyberinfrastructure Collaborative and the Encyclopedia of Life.
- Continuing our successful training activities, including the Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course and Phyloinformatics Summer Internships.
- Hosting a third hackathon in the area of population genetics.
- Broadening participation by under-represented groups through informatics activities such as the hackathons, the summer course, and summer internships.
- Continuing our support for the informatics needs of sponsored scientists, including both existing collaborations and new ones that will arise in the next year.
- Continued development of the administrative database and NESCent website.

V EDUCATION AND OUTREACH: INITIATIVES, ACTIVITIES AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS

The Education and Outreach Group (EOG) at NESCent has continued to focus on key areas of our mission: outreach to the education and science communities, providing resources for educators, and outreach to underrepresented groups. We have worked to develop effective programs, to build collaborations, to expand on established resources, and to take advantage of NESCent's scientific expertise. We also provide a variety of services within NESCent, such as public affairs and web site maintenance, and in year 3 composed and distributed the first copy of our electronic newsletter (http://www.nescent.org/news/newsletter_4_07.php). A second newsletter is currently in production. A new capability in conjunction with the Informatics group is media production, including video capture of presentations, and a Podcast program based on the Evolution in the News series. EOG is also represented on the editorial board of the new Springer journal "Evolution: Education and Outreach." We have been working with the journal to publicize NESCent's resources for educators, as well as providing articles for the journal based on activities at NESCent.

The two working groups supported in previous years by the EOG, "Evolution Education" and "Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU)," have led to new working groups and projects, such as the Evolution Across the Curriculum working group and sabbatical scholar Joe Fail's Evolution Curriculum for 4th Graders. In addition, EOG continues to sit in on working groups and catalysis meetings at NESCent, which has allowed us to collaborate with participants on various educational projects.

EOG staff members have attended professional meetings for scientists, educators, and underrepresented groups to represent NESCent and provide resources (Appendix V.1). At the 2006 meeting of the Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS), EOG worked with NCEAS and AIBS to organize a panel discussion entitled "Exploring Careers in Evolution and Ecology." This panel was so well received that it has been expanded for the 2007 SACNAS meeting to include a behind the scenes field trip to the University of Kansas Natural History Museum and a showing of "A Flock of Dodos" in addition to a repeat of the panel discussion. This year we are partnering with NCEAS, AIBS, the Ecological Society of America (ESA), and the Society for the Study of Evolution (SSE) in this outreach effort. We continue to co-sponsor the Evolution Symposium at the National Association of Biology Teachers annual meeting. The 2006 symposium focused on Macroevolution, and was the first year that NESCent produced a CD of educational resources to support the program. The 2007 symposium is "Evolution: Applications in Human Health and Populations," and we are producing a CD for 2007 that includes interviews with participants in the "Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations" catalysis meeting held at NESCent. NESCent is represented by EOG personnel on the Education Committee for SSE.

Dr. Greg Gibson, who has served as the Associate Director of EOG since NESCent's inception, has accepted a new faculty position at the University of Queensland. Dr. Brian Wiegmann, Professor of Entomology at NCSU, is serving as the interim director pending NSF approval. Dr. Wiegmann has served on NESCent's Operations Committee since the winter of 2006 and participated in the development of the 2006 NABT CD. Director Kathleen Smith has played an increasingly prominent role in directing EOG as the group has become more involved in various aspects of NESCent, such as providing publicity and news coverage of NESCent events. Drs. Jory Weintraub and Kristin Jenkins are full-time, on-site and they are assisted by Elsa Youngsteadt, a graduate student in entomology at NCSU, and Diane Bosnjak, an undergraduate in science policy at NCSU.

EOG Sponsored and Facilitated Working Groups

SELECTION (December 2006, June 2007)

This working group was proposed by BioQUEST, a curriculum development consortium, to develop educational resources in evolution using NESCent's scientific resources and connections. EOG personnel Kristin Jenkins and Jory Weintraub, as well as NESCent post-docs Kirsten Fisher, Samantha Price and David Kidd, were active participants. The "Phanerozoic Body Size" working group at NESCent was very interested in developing an educational piece, and EOG arranged for a representative of this working group, Jennifer Stempien, to join the SELECTION group. The second meeting of this group was held in conjunction with BioQUEST's summer workshop in Beloit, WI and NESCent arranged for access to the recently published datasets on lactose intolerance in African populations to be used for curriculum development. A desiccation tolerance problem space was also developed through NESCent and presented at the Botanical Congress in July. NESCent is also working with the BioQUEST BIRRD database as an education example for the NESCent Data Repository project (DRYAD).

Evolution Education 2006

This catalysis meeting was organized by the EOG and held in the summer of 2006. It resulted in two EOG sponsored working groups: Evolution Across the Curriculum and Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education (TREE). Current NESCent sabbatical scholar Malcolm Schug decided to apply for a sabbatical at NESCent as a result of this meeting.

Evolution Across the Curriculum

This group will address the problem of presentation of evolution as a separate and isolated concept in undergraduate science curricula. They will design educational resources to encourage the incorporation of evolution throughout biology courses, as well as in more specific courses such as botany or microbiology. The EOG and NESCent postdocs will be active in this group which has its first meeting in October 2007.

Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education (TREE)

This group will focus on identifying and addressing the misconceptions surrounding the use and interpretation of phylogenetic trees. The group will involve EOG and NESCent researchers and also has their initial meeting in October 2007.

Evolution Education in Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU)

This group was also convened by the EOG. The main goal of this group, which met in September 2005 and February 2006, was to identify and address issues and challenges associated with teaching evolution at historically minority universities (HMUs) and Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs). The participants were drawn from HMUs/MSIs across the country and included faculty from Black, Hispanic and Native American serving institutions. The group identified several key areas and projects which NESCent has proceeded to act upon. First, the group encouraged NESCent to offer a targeted sabbatical for faculty at HMUs which would combine research and the opportunity to develop educational materials. John Clamp, of North Carolina Central University, was the first targeted sabbatical scholar and he developed twin databases to allow students and recruiters to identify one another. EOG continues to maintain this database. Joe Fail, of Johnson C. Smith University, was at NESCent in the 2006-2007

academic year and developed an evolutionary biology curriculum for elementary students and a teacher training course based on the curriculum. NESCent is also partnering with SSE to provide travel awards for students and faculty from HMUs to attend the annual Evolution meetings. Finally, NESCent has begun collecting data on the prevalence of evolution courses at HMUs for further work by this group.

EOG partnerships with NESCent Science Working groups

EOG staff members participate in each NESCent sponsored working group or catalysis meeting. This assists us in disseminating the results of these groups, and also leads to potential collaborations. Several such collaborations have been initiated.

The members of the “Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space” are interested in developing educational materials based on the databases they are generating. Jennifer Stempien, a member of the working group who is doing a postdoc in science education, is coordinating this effort with EOG. We expect to be working closely with them at their next meeting, and possibly with Stempien in the interim as databases are constructed.

Ten participants, including the organizers, of the “Evolution in Contemporary Human Populations” catalysis meeting gave videotaped interviews on evolutionary medicine and their research. These interviews will be used on the educational resource CD NESCent is developing for the Evolution Symposium at NABT.

Joel Cracraft, an organizer of the working group “Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography,” is interested in offering a workshop in biogeography at a national educators meeting, such as NABT or the National Science Teachers Association (NSTA). EOG is working with him to arrange the workshop.

Several members of the Plant EvoGenetics working group expressed interest in educational activities ranging from bioinformatics to outreach to underrepresented minorities. EOG has introduced participants of this meeting to others for potential collaborations and will continue to look for opportunities to take advantage of this group's interest.

EOG Programs

Evolution in the News

Evolution in the News was designed to provide educators with current, interesting, and socially relevant evolutionary research in a format they could use in their classes. The stories are chosen from the primary literature (Science, PNAS, Evolution, etc.) and written up for students and teachers. Links to the primary literature and popular coverage are provided. Recently we have added a section of discussion questions and educational resources. In conjunction with the Science Journalism Internship, we have launched a podcast version of Evolution in the News. These podcasts will include audio recordings of the Evolution in the News stories, augmented with images, but will also include video clips of scientists talking about their research. We have written an NSF CCLI grant to fund further development and assessment of this program. (Appendix V.2)

Post-Doctoral Professional Development Program

The EOG runs a post-doctoral professional development program open to NESCent and local University postdocs and Ph.D. students. This program is detailed in our workshop section below.

Support of Center Activities

EOG also provides a variety of in house services at NESCent that support the aims of outreach and education. These include the organization of the Friday seminar series, NESCent website maintenance, including stories and news items, NESCent's quarterly newsletter production, serving as press officers for the Center, production and supply of posters/postcards/ads and booth orders for conferences, videoconferencing, video streaming of seminars and other presentations.

Priorities for year 4

In addition to continuing the very successful programs discussed above, in year 4, the EOG has a number of priorities for new activities.

- We plan to expand minority outreach activities. We hope to re-activate the Evolution Education at Historically Minority Universities (EEHMU) working group, to continue development with the SSE a scholarship program to bring students from HUM/MSI to the annual Evolution meeting, and continue our outreach to local HMU/MSI in the local region.
- Based on our previous experiences at the NABT conference, we intend to explore expanding our interactions with additional groups such as the National Science Teachers Association (NSTA) regional meetings and also select state science teacher conferences.
- EOG is collaborating with the Duke Institute for Genome Science and Policy (IGSP) to develop a summer course in genomics and evolution for faculty from primarily teaching institutions.
- EOG is also working with the NESCent working group "Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography" to develop a workshop for teachers in biogeography emphasizing the evolutionary aspects of this field.

VI CENTER COURSES, WORKSHOPS AND EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMS

NESCent has offered a number of courses to a variety of audiences in year 3. In subsequent years we will continue and expand these efforts.

Informatics

Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course

A Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course was held at NESCent in July 2007 (http://www.nescent.org/summer_course). It was organized principally by William Piel of Yale University, in collaboration with CIPRES. Twenty-three students spent eleven intense days learning phylogenetic programming skills in Java and Perl, and also learned how to use and contribute to the Mesquite and HyPhy software packages. They were taught by a team of nine internationally renowned instructors. Tuition waivers and travel scholarships were offered to increase participation by underrepresented groups. Despite the severe paucity of females in the field of informatics, approximately half the students in the summer course were women.

BioPerl Phylogenomics Tutorial

In a training activity that grew out of the 2006 Phyloinformatics Hackathon, two of the participants in that event, Jason Stajich and Albert Vilella, prepared a half-day tutorial at the 2007 ISMB conference in Vienna entitled “Implementing phylogenetic workflows for comparative genomics using BioPerl.” The materials from that tutorial have been made freely available from NESCent’s phyloinformatics wiki:

www.nescent.org/wg/phyloinformatics/images/9/99/ISMB2007tutorial-handouts.pdf

Summer of Code Internships

NESCent participated as a mentoring organization in the 2007 Google Summer of Code (phylosoc.nescent.org, Appendix VI.1). In this program, students receive a stipend from Google to spend a full summer contributing to any of over 100 distributed open source programming projects under the mentorship of experienced developers. The distributed network of mentors that remotely guided NESCent’s eleven Summer of Code students was assembled from among the participants of the 2006 Phyloinformatics Hackathon and from our collaborators in the GMOD project. The majority of mentors and students met at NESCent in August 2007 for a highly enjoyable end-of-summer wrap-up.

EOG

Post-Doctoral Professional Development Program

The post-doctoral professional development program was designed to provide NESCent post-doctoral fellows with career development information and opportunities they might miss in this non-traditional position. EOG organizes this program and identifies appropriate speakers in topics ranging from career advice to use of technology in teaching. These sessions are open to the public and often have postdocs and graduate students from local Universities in attendance. Sabbatical faculty and the directors have provided valuable career advice in special sessions of the NESCent informal seminar series. Media specialists have provided training in communicating with the media and the public. EOG has provided information about resources for post-doctoral fellows, such as the Duke Post-Doctoral Association, as well as training in

teaching. EOG also coordinates the visiting lecturers program which provides postdocs with the opportunity to give lectures in person at local institutions, including HMUs; remote lectures are also an option via videoconferencing (several NESCent scientists delivered guest lectures via videoconference to a Bioinformatics course at The University of Puerto Rico during the Spring 2007 semester). EOG staff have also provided individual and group consulting to postdocs on topics such as effective teaching, developing a Teaching Philosophy statement, scientific writing and delivering effective presentations.

NESCent Targeted Sabbatical Scholars

Joe Fail, a targeted sabbatical scholar, produced an exciting and innovative curriculum for teaching evolution in elementary schools. Together with the North Carolina School of Science and Math (a public high school), we obtained funds from Duke University to support a workshop for 15 local teachers on this curriculum. This program was an enormous success, and the School of Science and Math would like to continue this in the future. We are attempting to raise funds to make this a continuing program. This course focused on a highly integrated approach to science for elementary school students, and provided the teachers with important science education, and teaching tools. One of the most important aspects of this course was that the teachers attending were all from North Carolina public schools and about half of the teachers came from school districts where a very high percentage of students were minority (32-94%). This course received fabulous reviews (Appendix VI.2)

VII SUMMARY OF YEAR 3 CENTER ACTIVITIES TO INCREASE PARTICIPATION OF MEMBERS OF UNDERREPRESENTED GROUPS

Although many activities to increase the participation of underrepresented groups into science were discussed in the above report from our Education and Outreach group, we here summarize overall center activities. It is important to emphasize that this is a Center-wide commitment that permeates all of the center's activities. Specific activities in year 3 included:

In year 3 NESCent has sponsored the scientific work of several outstanding evolutionary biologists who are also African American, including Joe Hereford (postdoc), Paul Magwene (working group PI) and Clara Jones (visiting scholar from Fayetteville State University). Scott Edwards and Paul Turner are members of our SAB and Science Review Boards respectively.

Professor Joe Fail from Johnson C. Smith University was supported as a "targeted sabbatical scholar" (see <http://www.nescent.org/science/fullsabbatical.php>). Fail produced a highly innovative curriculum, discussed above.

Our student research internship (see Appendix VII.1 & VII.2) has brought 16 undergraduates, including many women and two African American undergraduate to the Center; 9 graduate students; and 3 students who recently graduated, for a total of 28 student research internships.

Our Computational Phyloinformatics course offered travel awards to students from underrepresented groups in an attempt to attract additional students from these populations. The course had almost 50% women students, who are highly under-represented in computational biology.

We developed an impressive set of programs for the SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science) meeting as detailed in the EOG report. This program has been highly successful.

We hosted a visit from a science class at NC AT&T to the Center. This group received brief presentations from postdoctoral fellows and had an opportunity to learn more about graduate programs in Evolutionary Biology, ask questions of the postdocs and other NESCent scientists, and participate in a hands-on evolution learning activity led by EOG staff.

Our evolution in the news Podcast proposal is in part targeted towards students from underrepresented groups.

VIII NESCENT ADMINISTRATION

The development of NESCent as a functioning center has continued in year 3. Major administrative activities and accomplishments include the following:

Meeting of the NESCent Senior Advisory Board

In August of 2007 our Senior Advisory Board met with NESCent and NSF program officers. This meeting was extremely productive, allowing us to discuss many important challenges facing the Center. A copy of the SAB report is included as Appendix VIII.1. In addition to our discussions about the operation and priorities of the Center, issues of the role of the SAB in reporting to NSF were resolved. Several new members were added, David Hillis replaced Barbara Schaal as Chair, and a rotation cycle was worked out for future years.

Duke University Provost's fund

Duke University provides external funding to NESCent for activities beyond the scope of the grant. In year 3 activities funded by these monies included: purchase of furniture for additional scientists and for the large seminar room; interview and recruitment expenses for informatics staff; partial salary for staff members; sponsorship of the summer course for elementary school teachers; co-sponsorship with the ARC-NZ Vegetative Function Research Network for a working group in wood evolution; incidental expenses associated with hosting meetings of organizations such as the editorial boards of several journals, the joint ATol/Barcode of Life meeting, and so forth; sponsorship of two Triangle working groups, receptions for meeting groups and NESCent scientist and NESCent social activities.

Staffing

In year 3 NESCent hired one additional staff member for administrative and IT support (webmaster, database curation, help-desk functions) from the core grant, and 4 additional members of the informatics team, largely from external grants (Appendix VIII.2)

Administrative Infrastructure

Administrative Database

We have continued to work on our administrative database, and project deployment before the year 4 site visit. The development of this database has occupied a considerable percentage of the core Informatics staff effort over the past year.

The NESCent Website

A new NESCent website was deployed in January of year 3. This highly informative, easily accessible website is an enormous advance over the previous website (Appendix IV.8).

5. Building the NESCent Community

We have developed a number of activities to improve the sense of community of onsite NESCent scientists and staff including a number of social events including happy hours, meals, picnics and the like. We also generally host a reception for working groups and catalysis meetings so that visitors may informally interact with onsite scientists, to increase the likelihood of broader

collaboration and impact. Funding for social activities is provided by money from the Duke University Provost Fund.

A NESCent retreat was held in the fall of 2006; a second one is planned for early January in 2008.

IX PRODUCTS FROM NESCENT FUNDED ACTIVITIES IN YEAR 3**PUBLICATIONS*****Publications: Postdoctoral Fellows***

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Hoeksema J.D., and S. Forde. A meta-analysis of factors affecting local adaptation between species. In review, *The American Naturalist*.

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Eyre-Walker, A. & Keightley, P.D. (2007) The distribution of fitness effects of new mutations. *Nature Reviews Genetics* 8, 610-618

Stoletzki, N. & **Eyre-Walker, A.** (2007) Synonymous Codon Use in *Escherichia coli* - Selection for translational accuracy. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 24, 374-381.

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Mandegar, M. A., and **S. P. Otto** (2007) Mitotic recombination counteracts the benefits of genetic segregation. *Proceedings of the Royal Society, London B.*, 274: 1301-1307. [Analysis & writing completed at NESCent]

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Johnston, M.O., E. Porcher, J.K. Kelly, P.-O. Cheptou, C.G. Eckert, E. Elle, M.A. Geber, C. Goodwillie, S. Kalisz, D.A. Moeller, R.H. Ree, R. D. Sargent, M. Vallejo-Mara, A. A. Winn. Genetic correlations among fertility components are likely to maintain mixed mating in plants. Planned for *American Naturalist* submission in fall 2007.

Porcher, E., J.K. Kelly, P.-O. Cheptou, C.G. Eckert, E. Elle, M.A. Geber, C. Goodwillie, M.O. Johnston, S. Kalisz, D.A. Moeller, R.H. Ree, R.D. Sargent, M. Vallejo-Mara, A.A. Winn. The genetic consequences of fluctuating inbreeding depression and the evolution of plant mating systems. Planned for fall 2007 submission to Journal of Evolutionary Biology or Genetical Research.

Eckert, C.G., S. Kalisz, M.A. Geber, P.-O. Cheptou, E. Elle, C. Goodwillie, M.O. Johnston, J.K. Kelly, D.A. Moeller, E. Porcher, R.H. Ree, R.D. Sargent, M. Vallejo-Mara, A.A. Winn. Conceptual and experimental tools for understanding how pollination ecology influences the evolution of plant mating systems. Planned for fall 2007 submission to TREE.

Moeller, D.A., R.D. Sargent, P.-O. Cheptou, C.G. Eckert, E. Elle, M.A. Geber, C. Goodwillie, M.O. Johnston, S. Kalisz, J.K. Kelly, E. Porcher, R.H. Ree, M. Vallejo-Mara, A.A. Winn. Comparative analysis of plant mating-systems.

Goodwillie, C., P.-O. Cheptou, C.G. Eckert, E. Elle, M.A. Geber, M.O. Johnston, S. Kalisz, J.K. Kelly, D.A. Moeller, E. Porcher, R.H. Ree, R.D. Sargent, M. Vallejo-Mara, A.A. Winn. Mating-system evolution and floral allocation: macro- and microevolutionary patterns. Planned for Evolution.

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Publications: Catalysis Meetings

Russell, A. L., J. Ranivo, E. P. Palkovacs, S. M. Goodman, and A. D. Yoder. 2007. Working at the interface of phylogenetics and population genetics: a biogeographical analysis of *Triaenops* spp. (Chiroptera: Hipposideridae). *Molecular Ecology* 16:839-851.

Russell, A. L., S. M. Goodman, and M. P. Cox. In prep. Coalescent analyses support multiple main-to-island dispersals in the evolution of Malagasy *Triaenops* bats (Chiroptera: Hipposideridae). *Systematic Biology*.

C. Kremen, A. Cameron, A. Moilanen, S. Phillips, H. Beentje, J. Dransfeld, B. L. Fisher, F. Glaw, R. Hijmans, D. C. Lees, E. Louis, C. Raxworthy, G. Schatz, M. Vences, D. R. Vieites, P. C. Wright, M.L.Zjhra. 2007. Aligning conservation priorities across taxa in Madagascar, a biodiversity hotspot. To be submitted to *Nature*.

Leebens-Mack J, Vision T, Brenner E, Bowers JE, Cannon S and 21 others (2006) Taking the first steps towards a standard for reporting in phylogenies: Minimal Information About a Phylogenetic Analysis (MIAPA). *OMICS* 10, 231-237. doi:10.1089/omi.2006.10.231

Publications: Other Meetings and Activities

Lapp H, Bala S, Balhoff JP, Bouck A, Goto N, Holder M, Holland R, Holloway A, Katamaya T, Lewis PO, Mackey A, Osborne BI, Piel WH, Kosakovsky-Pond SL, Poon A, Qiu W-G, Stajich JE, Stoltzfus A, Thierer T, Vilella AJ, Vos RA, Zmasek CM, Zwickl D, Vision TJ (accepted pending revision) The 2006 NESCent Phyloinformatics Hackathon: A field report. *Evolutionary Bioinformatics*.

Ahmed Moustafa and Debashish Bhattacharya. 2007. Phylogenomic analysis identifies *Plantae* genes with chlamydia origin. (Preparing)

Kohn, David. 2008. Darwin's keystone: the principle of divergence. In *The Cambridge Companion to the Origin of Species*, Robert Richards and Michael Ruse, eds. Cambridge University Press. (forthcoming)

Gilchrist, G. W., and C. Lee. 2007. All stressed out and nowhere to go: does evolvability limit adaptation in invasive species? *Genetica* 129:127-132.

Terry, M. 2008 (2004). One nation, under the Designer. Pp. 402-411 in . J.W. Noll, ed. *Taking sides: clashing views on educational issues*. 14th ed., expanded. McGraw-Hill, Dubuque, IA.

Terry, M. 2007. What's design got to do with it?: Independent schools and the teaching of science. *Independent School*. 66(2):40-47.

Beder, J. H., and R. Gomulkiewicz. Optimizing selection for function-valued traits. *Journal of Mathematical Biology*. (Accepted 27 June 2007).

Griswold, C. K., R. Gomulkiewicz, and N. Heckman. Hypothesis testing in comparative and experimental studies of function-valued traits. *Evolution*. (In revision; submitted 22 June 2007)

Tsai YE, Fox JR, Kidd D. 2007. PhyloGeoViz: A Phylogeographic visualization tool. In prep.

Software and Databases

Software and databases: Postdoctoral Fellows

Kidd, D. M., and X. Liu. GEOPHYLOBUILDER 1.0
<http://www.nescent.org/informatics/software.php>

Hoeksema J. D. SAS code for conducting mixed-model meta-regression analysis in SAS.

Hoeksema J. D. and S. Forde. 2007. Summary data on local adaptation, species traits, and experimental design across 29 cross-inoculation studies of species interactions.

Tsai YE, Fox JR, **Kidd D.** 2007. PhyloGeoViz: A Phylogeographic visualization tool.
<http://phylogeoviz.org>.

Software and databases Sabbatical Scholars and Visitors

Jones, C.B., R.H. Horwich, and R.C. Brockett, R.C. 2006. Demography of black howler monkeys (*Alouatta pigra*) in two habitats at the Community "Baboon" Sanctuary (CBS), Belize, Central America. NESCent Archive.

Software and databases Working Groups

Mark Gibson and Nicole Washington. 2007. Phenote working group. www.phenote.org

Ree, R. H. and S. A. Smith. 2007. Lagrange: likelihood analysis of geographic range evolution.
<http://code.google.com/p/lagrange>

Johnston and Kalicz. Plant mating system database. The final database will comprise four separate databases.

- 1) The mating system database contains information on estimates of selfing/outcrossing rate and/or the inbreeding coefficient measured at the population level for 475 species.
- 2) The inbreeding depression database contains information on estimates inbreeding depression measured across the life history (3-stage or 4-stage IBD) measured at the population level.
- 3) The experimental pollination database contains information at the population level on experimental tests of selfing, outcrossing, pollen limitation, reproductive assurance, timing of selfing, etc.
- 4) The species traits database contains data on the average morphological, phenological, life history and habitat characteristics for all 475 species in the mating system database.

Significantly, all four databases contain citations to the original publications from which the data were extracted.

Software and databases: Other Meetings and Activities

Holland R., Balhoff K., Thierer T. 2006. BioJava (Phylogenetics extensions).
<http://www.biojava.org/>

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<http://www.biojava.org/>

James C. Estill, Hilmar Lapp, William Piel. 2007. Command line topological query application for BioSQL.
https://www.nescent.org/wg_phyloinformatics/PhyloSoC:Command_Line_Topological_Query_Application_for_BioSQL

Osborne, B.I., and S. Cain. 2007. The new GMOD Wiki with complete GMOD documentation.
<http://www.gmod.org>

Nowak, MD, C. Simpson, and D Zwickl. 2007. Single Node Age Prior Estimator (SNAPE) v. 0.9.

Jason E Stajich. 2007. BioPerl Population Genetics Modules. <http://bioperl.org>

Stajich JE. 2007. Comparative Genomics Tools in BioPerl. <http://bioperl.org>

PROPOSALS AND GRANTS***Postdoctoral Fellows***

Hoeksema J.D., S. Brewer, D. Reed, C. Jackson, M. Holland, C. Ochs, G. Stratton, S. Threlkeld. 2007. University of Mississippi. Graduate Training in Multi-Scale Approaches to Forest Restoration and Management Science. USDA. 5 years. \$252,000.

Steven Jansen & **Amy Zanne**. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Evolutionary trends of water transport systems in woody plants. Bentham-Moxon Trust. 4 weeks. £2000

Proposals and grants: Sabbatical Scholars and Visitors

Tang J, Szekely L, Vision TJ. 2006. Phylogenetic Analysis with Complex Gene Rearrangement Events. NIH/NSF. 3 yrs. \$254,016 D&I to UNC.

W. O. McMillan/R. Reed. 2007. North Carolina State University/University of California at Irvine. The molecular basis of mimicry in Heliconius. NSF (DEB-0715096. Feb 2007-Feb 2010. \$460,000.P.I.

John Clamp 2007. N.C. Central University. A Taxonomic Revision and Phylogenetic Investigation of Five Groups of Species in the Genus Vorticella (Protista, Ciliophora, Oligohymenophorea). NSF DEB \$360,000 over 3 years (begins October, 2007).

Proposals and Grants: Working Groups

Mathews.,S., R. Beaman, C. Campbell, S. Ickert-Bond, A. Liston, L. Raubeson, G. Rothwell, A. Schwarzbach, & D. Stevenson. 2006. Harvard University, Yale University, Univ. of Maine, Univ. of Alaska, Oregon State Univ., Central Washington Univ., Ohio University, Univ. of Texas-Brownsville, & New York Botanical Garden. Gymnosperms on the Tree of Life: Resolving the Phylogeny of Seed Plants. NSF: EF-0629817. Oct. 1, 2006-Sept. 30, 2010. \$2,999,983.

Mabee P, Westerfield M, Vision TJ. 2007. Linking evolution to genomics using phenotype ontologies. NSF. 3 yrs. \$1,050,944 D&I to UNC.

A. Stoltzfus, G. Gupta and E. Pontelli. Development of an intelligent system for evolutionary analysis. NIH. 4 years. \$175 K direct costs per year.

Elizabeth Elle and Mark O. Johnston. The paradox of mixed mating in plants. 23 August 2007. European Society for Evolutionary Biology XI Congress, Uppsala, Sweden. Two invited speakers and five contributed talks. Three of the talks were from the working group.

Proposals and grants: Catalysis Meetings

David Vieites, Craig Moritz, Miguel Vences, Olga Ramilijaona, Noromalala Raminosa, Sandra Nieto-Romin. 2007. University of California Berkeley. Identifying Evolutionary Hotspots and Priority Areas for the Conservation of the Amphibians of Madagascar. MacArthur FOundation. 3 years. \$345,000, in review.

Lees, D.C. [Anthony, N., Vieites, D., Ranaivosolo R. co-PI's/collaborators] 2007. Natural History Museum [University of New Orleans, University of California at Berkeley and University of Antananarivo]. Lepidoptera as probes of Pleistocene rainforest refugia and Holocene forest fragmentation history in Madagascar. For 1 year. Proposal submitted 28 March 2007, decision awaited.

Weigel, D and D. Reznick. Application for genome sequencing of poeciliids to NIH.

Byers, P.H. and Govindaraju, D. R. 2007. Evolution and Medicine. Special Plenary Symposium at the 2007 American Society of Human Genetics. San Diego, CA.

Clark, A. G., Govindaraju, D. R., Mackay, T. F.C. and Stearns, S. C. 2007. Measuring evolutionary change in modern human populations using cohort data. Proposal submitted to NESCent to form a working group. Reviewed - Final Decision Pending.

Ellison, P. E., Govindaraju, D. R., Nesse, R. M. and Stearns, S. C. 2007. Evolution in Health and Medicine. Proposal submitted to the Sackler Colloquia of the National Academy of Sciences for extending the ideas generated at the NESCent supported Catalysis meeting.

Kimberly Hughes (University of Illinois, Champaign Urbana), Anne Houde (Lake Forest College), Helen Rodd (University of Toronto) 2007, Collaborative Research/RUI: Behavioral and Genetic Mechanisms for Frequency-Dependent Survival and Mating Advantage in Guppies. Submitted to NSF as 2 linked collaborative proposals (4 years, approx \$500K total).

Lees, D.C. Natural History Museum. In collaboration with David Vieites (UC Berkeley) and Nicola Anthony (University of New Orleans). "Lepidoptera as probes of Pleistocene rainforest refugia and Holocene forest fragmentation history in Madagascar". National Geographic Society. 1 year. \$19,750.

Proposals and grants: Other Meetings and Activities

G. W. Gilchrist, 2007. College of William and Mary. Evolution of performance curves in seasonal environments. NSF/NESCent sabbatical leave. 2008-09.

Holmes I, Stein L, Vision TJ. 2007. Enhancement of the GBrowse genome annotation browser. NIH. 3 yrs. \$384,000 to UNC.

Smith KK, Greenberg J, Piel W, Michener C, Antelman K, Vision TJ. pending.

A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying

Published Works in Evolutionary Biology. NSF. 3 yrs. \$2,180,169 total.

Michener W, Jones M, Smith K, Cook R, Frame M, Lapp H, Servilla M, Vieglais D. pending. INTEROP: Creation of a Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences. NSF. 3 yrs. \$50,800 D&I to Duke."

"David Kohn. 2006. American Museum of Natural History. Darwin\'s Evolutionary Botany. NSF. 3 years. \$231,567.

David Kohn & Christie Stephenson. 2007. American Museum of Natural History. Darwin Manuscript Project. NSF. 3 years. \$306,893."

X CENTER PARTNERSHIPS AND ASSOCIATIONS

NESCent entered into a diverse array of partnerships for a variety of activities during year 3 of funding. These include:

From the start, NESCent has had a strong relationship with NCEAS. The Directors are in frequent contact (and the Director of NCEAS has provided invaluable advice to the NESCent Director), we have jointly funded 3 working groups thus far, and have partnered on data sharing initiatives. NCEAS is also a co-sponsor of our SACNAS activities.

<http://www.nceas.ucsb.edu>

NESCent has collaborated extensively with the Evolutionary Genomics Center (EGC) of Duke's Institute for Genome Science and Policy. The EGC Director, Greg Wray, is a member of our operations committee; the Center jointly sponsored our 2007 Darwin Day symposium on Genomes and Evolution and the EGC is currently working with our EOG group to develop a summer workshop for faculty at primarily teaching institutions

<http://www.genome.duke.edu/centers/ceg>

We are developing a collaboration with the Carolina Population Center at UNC, to explore methods to quantify the patterns and effectiveness of collaborative research at interdisciplinary research centers like NESCent and CPC.

<http://www.cpc.unc.edu/>

NESCent informatics has partnered with the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) to obtain funding for a helpdesk and user support.

<http://www.gmod.org>

NESCent's funded project linking evolution to genomics using phenotype ontologies involves a partnership with the National Center for Biomedical Ontologies (NCBO) and the Zebrafish Information Network (ZFIN)

<http://www.bioontology.org>

<http://zfin.org>

A pending proposal to develop a digital repository for data in evolutionary biology (DRYAD) involves partnerships with the UNC School of Information & Library Sciences Metadata Research Center, the North Carolina State University Digital Libraries Initiative, the LTER Network and TreeBASE, as well as major evolutionary biology journals and societies, including American Naturalist, Evolution, Society for the Study of Evolution, Integrative and Comparative Biology, Journal of Evolutionary Biology, Molecular Biology and Evolution, Molecular Ecology, and Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution, Society of Systematics Biology, Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution, National Center for Biotechnology Information, European Society for Evolutionary Biology, German National Library of Science and Technology

<http://ils.unc.edu/mrc/>

<http://www.lib.ncsu.edu/dli/>

<http://www.lternet.edu/>

<http://www.treebase.org>

Our INTEROP proposal includes a partnership with the LTER network, NCEAS, the Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center, the USGS National Biological Information Infrastructure and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)

<http://www-eosdis.ornl.gov/>

<http://www.nbio.gov>

<http://www.gbif.org>

The Phyloinformatics Hackathon was in partnership with member projects of the Open Bioinformatics Foundation

http://www.open-bio.org/wiki/Main_Page

With Google's sponsorship we ran the Summer of Code for Phyloinformatics

<http://code.google.com/soc/2007/>

We collaborate with developers at the San Diego Supercomputer Center (SDSC) to define application programming interfaces (APIs) for the CIPRES portal.

<http://www.sdsc.edu>

http://www.phylo.org/sub_sections/portal

Our 2006 summer course in phyloinformatics was with co-sponsorship from CIPRES (Cyberinfrastructure for Phylogenetic Research)

<http://www.phylo.org>

We are in the process of developing an active collaboration with the Encyclopedia of Life Initiative, with collaborations with their informatics, education and outreach groups, and synthesis center

<http://www.eol.org>

We are developing a collaboration with a set of museum databases (HerpNet, ORNIS, MaNIS and BioGeomancer) to help develop a long term plan for expansion, development of community standards and long term sustainability of these valuable databases.

<http://www.herpnet.org/>

<http://www.specifysoftware.org/Informatics/informaticornis/>

<http://manisnet.org/>

<http://www.biogeomancer.org/>

NESCent has worked with the Australian-New Zealand Research Network for Vegetation Function to co-sponsor a multi day working group on wood evolution. In addition, NESCent, along with NCEAS and QUEST have formed a "Networks International Council;" this group meets by conference call ~2X per year to discuss potential collaborations and issues.

<http://www.vegfunction.net>

<http://quest.bris.ac.uk/>

We have worked with the Society for the Study of Evolution (SSE) on several projects, including the development of DRYAD, co-sponsorship of NESCent's SACNAS activities, and co-sponsorship of the presentation at the NABT annual meeting. An EOG staff member is a member of the SSE Education Committee.

<http://www.evolutionarysociety.org>

The American Institute of Biological Science (AIBS) has been an active partner with NESCent from the start. Currently they are co-sponsors of both the NABT Evolution Symposium and NESCent's SACNAS activities.

<http://www.aibs.org/core/index.html>

NESCent has worked actively with the Ecological Society of America (ESA) in efforts to develop digital data registries and repositories for the evolutionary and ecological sciences. In addition, the ESA is a co-sponsor of our SACNAS activities.

<http://www.esa.org>

We have developed a strong relation with Springer Press. EOG staff members and NESCent Sabbatical Scholars are members of the editorial board of the new Springer journal (Evolution: Education and Outreach). In addition, Springer is providing financial support for NESCent's SACNAS activities.

<http://www.springer.com/east/home/life+sci?SGWID=5-10027-70-173740503-0&detailsPage=journal%7Cdescription>

Sigma Xi, the Scientific Research Society, will be a co-sponsor of our 2008 Darwin Day symposium on the Origin and Early Evolution of Life.

<http://www.sigmaksi.org>

NESCent's EOG group is collaborating with the North Carolina Association for Biomedical Research (NCABR) on education and outreach projects.

<http://www.ncabr.org/>

We are participating with the North Carolina Museum of Natural History in their Science Café series.

www.naturalsciences.org

We are participating with the Coalition for the Public Understanding of Science (COPUS) in public education initiatives.

<http://www.copusproject.org>

We worked with the North Carolina School of Science and Math to offer a summer course in teaching evolutionary biology at the elementary school level to teachers.

<http://www.ncssm.edu>

XI NESCENT EXTERNAL FUNDING**Funded*****Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies (Appendix IV.7)***

Subaward through University of South Dakota (PI: Paula Mabee)

National Science Foundation BDI-0641025 (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$853,338

NESCent Total Amount: \$1,050,945

06/01/2007 - 5/31/2010

Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser (Appendix IV.6)

Subaward through University of California at Berkeley (PI: I. Holmes)

National Institutes of Health (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$242,565

NESCent Total Amount: \$310,482 (D&I to UNC),

4/1/2007 - 3/31/2010

Development of the www.EcoliCommunity.org Information Resource

Subaward through Texas A&M Research Foundation (PI: Jim Hu)

National Institute of General Medical Science (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$30,550

NESCent Total Amount: \$39,104

06/01/07 – 05/31/09

Pending***A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology (Appendix IV.4)***

National Science Foundation, BD&I (PI: Kathleen Smith and Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$1,907,531

NESCent Total Amount: \$2,180,169 (D&I)

06/01/08 – 05/31/11

Evolution in the News Podcasts from the National Evolutionary Synthesis Center (Appendix V.2)

National Science Foundation, CCLI (PI: Kathleen Smith and Kristin Jenkins)

Total Direct Costs: \$116,720

Total Amount: \$150,000

11/01/07 – 10/31/09

INTEROP: Creation of an International Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences (Appendix IV.5)

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: William Michener)

National Science Foundation (PIs: Kathleen Smith and Hilmar Lapp)

NESCent Total Direct: \$39,535

NESCent Total Amount: \$50,803

01/01/08 – 12/31/10

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